

Teachers' attitudes towards student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices: instruction efficacy in perspective

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ABSTRACT

The advancement of students' knowledge, skills, and other learning experiences is the goal of student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices, and teachers' attitudes toward implementing these principles are vital to ensure classroom instruction efficacy. From this standpoint, this study aimed to examine English as a foreign language (EFL) teachers' attitude toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in the Saudi EFL context concerning classroom instruction efficacy. Also, it correlated the participants' responses with their gender, experience, degree, and specialization. The descriptive survey design was used to achieve the study objectives. The study tools, a questionnaire and a semi-structured interview were applied to a convenient sample of 73 faculty members. The results showed that the study sample (EFL teachers) had very positive attitudes towards pedagogy and assessment practices focused on students. In addition, the demographic variables of gender, experience, degree, and specialization had no significant role in affecting their responses to pedagogy and assessment practices. Finally, the interviewees expressed that the EFL classroom instruction efficacy can improve the situation in which students are more active, cooperative, responsible, engaged, communicative, and free. In light of the current results, the researchers proposed recommendations and implications.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices, where the learners dominate the learning process, connect with a model of learning that advocates a paradigm transformation in both teaching and learning [1], [2]. This shift, according to the scholars, should result in numerous differentiated tasks and activities, including relocating control from the teacher to the students and considering them as collaborators in the process of learning [3], replicating individual learners' differences and different necessities with particular prominence on the learner and learning [4], enhancing learners' critical thinking and autonomy [5], engaging students actively in learning process through practical exercises, conversations, and problem-solving sessions [6], providing suitable feedback to students [7]. Student-centered learning assessment practices require students to actively participate in creating goals for their learning and development, tracking their progress, and identifying any gaps. Additionally, student-centered assessment techniques like self-assessment, peer evaluation, and portfolios have the potential to assist students in acquiring essential self-regulatory abilities in addition to fundamental topic knowledge and skills [8], [9].

In this regard, teachers play a crucial role in the implementation and employment of student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices, and their views and attitudes toward the execution of those practices may affect classroom efficacy with special reference to student-centeredness. According to Sawant and Rizvi [10], attitude is characterized as an organized propensity to react favorably or unfavorably toward a given set of objects. Otara *et al.* [11] concluded that adopting a positive attitude toward learner-centered pedagogy is a crucial component of implementing a competency-based curriculum. In order to mitigate the many factors preventing teachers from adopting positive attitudes, all parties involved in education, including policymakers, should collaborate. Nworgu *et al.* [12] described attitude as a mental state of preparedness that has been formed via learning experiences having a direct or dynamic impact on how individuals react to all things. Likewise, in teaching, a technique of instruction's use or nonuse depends on the interaction between attitudes and that method. Azuka *et al.* [13] opined that a teacher's attitude toward particular teaching techniques might affect how they are used in the classroom and even how they organize the content. Otara *et al.* [11] commented that instructors' attitudes affect how they prepare lessons, how they interact with students, the techniques employed, and the activities they decide to have them participate in.

The classroom administration, techniques, and other actions teachers employ, as well as their engagement with the students, are all revealed by their attitudes, beliefs, and understanding of student-centered learning and approaches. Shihiba [14] stated that teachers' attitudes, beliefs, and comprehension of student-centered learning have a significant impact on how they set up their classrooms, the methods, or activities they choose, and how they interact with the students. The students' attitudes toward language learning may progressively transform, and their interest in the subject may be excited, with favorable attitudes toward student-centered learning method. According to Farzaneh and Nejadansari [15], positive attitudes toward student-centered learning strategies may gradually change students' attitudes toward language learning and stimulate their interest. The benefit of having a favorable attitude toward student-centered learning strategies may include group projects which provide students the confidence to take on obstacles and enjoy learning. Salleh and Yusoff [16] listed the advantages of positive attitudes toward student-centered learning methods.

Researchers contend that tasks like group projects provide students with the courage to face challenges and enjoy learning because they feel they can rely on one another for support. The employment and execution of any classroom practice and task come with high expectations and obligations, and teachers are the only ones who carry out those tasks and, in particular student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in the classroom. Therefore, they must maintain and show, preferably, positive attitudes that emphasize student-centered learning to ensure that goals of student-centeredness are met. The attitude and interactions of instructors with students, classmates, and the community must significantly shift for this objective to be achieved [17]. A curriculum that is interesting and relevant to students is more likely to be developed by teachers with a good attitude toward their subject. Additionally, they are more likely to be prepared to invest the time and energy necessary to develop a curriculum and teaching methodologies that are well-paced and planned.

Benard *et al.* [13] maintained that teachers' attitudes and beliefs may affect how they arrange the curriculum and the instructional strategies they employ in the classroom. A positive attitude is essential for instructors to successfully adopt and apply learner-centered pedagogy and assessment practices. If a teacher is enthusiastic about the subject, s/he can share that passion with the students. While a negative attitude makes a teacher more likely to be unenthusiastic and less likely to: convey that enthusiasm to the students, give the support they need to succeed and adapt to the student's needs. Otara *et al.* [11] commented that positive attitudes will encourage teachers to adopt and apply learner-centered pedagogy successfully, but a negative attitude would hinder it. This study therefore aimed at investigating English as a foreign language (EFL) teachers' attitude toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices concerning classroom instruction efficacy. The specific objectives of the current study are as: i) to identify teachers' attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in the EFL classroom; ii) to find out any significant difference in the participants' responses from gender, experience, degree, and specialization; and iii) to examine how student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices enhance EFL classroom instruction efficacy.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices depend greatly on the attitudes of the teachers. A teaching strategy known as learner-centered pedagogy puts student needs first. It strongly emphasizes teamwork, active learning, and student engagement. Additionally, assessment procedures should be learner-centered, which means that they should be created to assess students' growth and learning, keeping student-centeredness in mind. Teachers with positive attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment

practices are more likely to be enthusiastic about teaching, empathic, open to new ideas, and collaborative to ensure the efficacy of classroom instructions.

Several studies investigated student-centeredness in different contexts. For example, Plessis [18] investigated student teachers' attitudes regarding learner-centered pedagogy. The researcher recruited 38 teacher-training students for the study. The study sample had a poor insight of learner-centeredness beside considering learner-centered approach challenging if implemented. Also, Orabah *et al.* [19] examined English instructors' understanding and application of student-centered learning assessment. To discover more about instructors' perceptions regarding student-centered learning assessment, a questionnaire was employed. In addition to the questionnaires, interviews were employed to get additional specific information from the participants. The results of this study demonstrated that every English teacher has their own definition and understanding of student-centered learning assessment; however, it was challenging to comprehend teachers' definitions of student-centered learning assessment because there is not a standard definition for this term in the available literature.

In addition, Ebert-May *et al.* [20] examined student-centered instruction through seminars for professional development which aimed at helping teachers make the transition from teacher-to learner-centered approach. The participants were evaluated through self-reported survey and observation. The analysis revealed that the instructors believed they were taking a learner-centered approach but were actually not; they were using teacher-centered instruction. Also, Zolfaghari *et al.* [21] carried out a study to determine the degree to which English teachers' and students' attitudes were taken into account in terms of learner-centered pedagogy. Data was collected using one-sample and independent samples t-tests in a sample of 378 teacher training students and 196 instructors. The findings showed that, in teacher preparation programs, assessment practices do not align with learner-centered pedagogy.

It was also explored that learner-centered pedagogy and assessment practices still fall short. Likewise, Bremner [22] investigated learner-centered education from the teachers' viewpoints. This study employed a quantitative survey with 248 English language teachers to find out whether or not participants had heard of learner-centered education, how comfortable they felt defining it, how they would define it, and how useful they thought it was to their practice. According to the results, teachers had a broader comprehension of learner-centered education. Some elements, including active engagement, were thought to be crucial. It was noted that a more flexible, context-led approach to defining learner-centered education would be more effective than the various conflicting definitions found in the literature. Similarly, research by Salema [23] assessed the attitude of teachers and students toward the implementation of learner-centered pedagogy. The researcher adopted mixed research methods for data collection and analysis, involving 580 students and 115 teachers. They use questionnaires, in-depth interview guides, and observation guides. The findings indicated that students and teachers had positive attitudes toward implementing learner-centered pedagogy. Moreover, the findings indicated no significant differences between attitudes and mean scores of teachers based on their years of experience.

In addition, Salleh and Yusoff [16] conducted a study to examine teachers' attitudes and beliefs toward using Student-Centered Learning in English language classes. A survey and questionnaires were used as research instruments. In addition, the data from different assessments was collected to determine the relationship between student-centered learning practices and student achievement. The results showed positive attitudes of English language teachers toward student-centered learning. However, teachers employ student-centered and teacher-centered learning strategies in teaching the English language in primary school. Additionally, Otara *et al.* [11] conducted a study to look into the instructors' perceptions of learner-centered pedagogy. The study included 165 teachers, and the data was analyzed using simple percentages and chi-square analysis, and the results were verified using the questionnaire and interview answers. The findings indicate that instructors had negative attitudes regarding learner-centered pedagogy. It is, further, demonstrated that teachers' attitudes are unaffected by gender.

Moreover, studies on teachers' attitudes toward student-centeredness have been carried out, but the existing literature shows that they rarely investigated teachers' attitudes toward pedagogy and assessment practices altogether with special reference to classroom instruction efficacy. Therefore, the statement of the problem was reformulated to answer the following research questions: i) what are teachers' and students' attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in EFL classroom instruction; ii) are there any significant differences in the participants' responses from their gender, experience, degree, or specialization; and iii) how would student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices enhance EFL classroom instruction efficacy.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1. Research design

The descriptive survey design was used to achieve the study objectives. The study explored EFL teachers' attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in the Saudi EFL context concerning execution, challenges, and solutions. Also, it correlated the participants' responses with their gender, experience, degree, and specialization.

3.2. Population and sample of the study

The study was administered to 110 EFL teachers at a Saudi university in the southern western region of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. They are faculty members at the College of Languages and Translation and the Deanship of preparatory year. They come from various nationalities, such as Jordan, India, Egypt, Sudan, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Yemen, and Algeria. They have different degrees in English, including master's and doctorates in various majors. In addition, they have different experiences. Their English language is near-native or foreign.

The study sample was drawn by the convenience sampling technique. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling technique wherein components are chosen for the sample based on their accessibility to the researchers [24]. The study questionnaire was designed using Google Forms, and the questionnaire link was shared with the study population; the responses reached (73). A reasonable sample size is often approximately 10% of the population, as long as the sample size does not exceed 1,000. This would offer you a rough but nonetheless helpful indication of what their opinions were [25]. This study, however, chose the number which was closer to the maximum due to the researchers' access to the population. Furthermore, obtaining correct results is crucial. The study's demographic factors, including gender, experience, education, and specialization, were considered. The study was administered to 110 EFL teachers and the responses percentage reached 66.36%. Table 1 shows the distribution of the study sample. In addition, the participants were asked at the end of the questionnaire about doing an interview. Those who okayed their agreement added their contact information. The total number of interviewees was 20.

Table 1. Sample distribution according to their demography

Variable	Group	No.	%
Gender	Male	40	54.8
	Female	33	45.2
Degree	PhD	35	47.9
	Master	38	52.1
Specialization	Applied linguistics	37	50.7
	Linguistics	18	24.7
	Literature	18	24.7
Experience	1-5	15	20.5
	6-10	19	26.0
	Above 10	39	53.4
Total		73	100

3.3. Ethics statement

The study has been approved by the Ethics Committee at the Deanship of Scientific Research at Najran University. The code for the study was assigned as (NU/RG/SEHRC/12/14). Also, the participants' signed consent letter was collected.

3.4. Study tools

The study utilized two tools, a five point-Likert questionnaire and a semi-structured interview for collecting the data to answer the research questions. It used a closed-item questionnaire about EFL teachers' attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in the Saudi EFL context concerning execution, challenges, and solutions from the teachers' points of view. The researchers, based on the literature review, developed the questionnaire items and the questions for the semi-structured interview. The questionnaire consisted of three main sections: demographic data (gender, experience, degree, and specialization) and attitudes towards student-centered pedagogy practices (10 items) and student-centered assessment practices (10 items). The semi-structured interview searched for the challenges and solutions for the attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in the EFL classroom.

3.5. Validity

The validity of the study tools was ensured by face validity and internal consistency. In face validity, each item is examined to determine if it focuses on the traits that the instrument is intended to address. In this

procedure, the item is compared to its objectives and the construct's theoretical characteristics. Researchers meticulously assess each item to see if it helps, making sure that no detail is missed [26]. Nine experienced faculty members in the field of second language teaching assessed the current study tools if they could collect data to answer the study questions and thus achieve its objectives. Based on their reviews, they approved that the study tools can achieve the study objectives. Also, some modifications related to wordiness, language, the study context, and items and domains were present. The following issues were observed:

From to

Student-centered pedagogy practices

- Learner-autonomy self-learning
- Motivation motivational tasks
- Role play role-play activities
- Student reflection student reflection tasks

Student-centered assessment practices

- Summarizing and note taking summarizing, synthesizing, and note taking

Semi-structured interview question

From:

- How do you see student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices enhancing language learning?
- What are your attitudes in implementing student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices that in turn develop instruction efficiency?

To:

- What are (teachers') your views toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in enhancing EFL classroom instruction efficacy?

In addition, the study tool (questionnaire) was applied to a survey sample of 20 male and female teachers for internal consistency. Pearson's correlation coefficient was, then, calculated between items, domain, and the whole scale. Pearson correlation coefficient summarizes the features of a dataset. The degree and direction of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables are specifically described [27]. Table 2 presents the analysis results of the pilot study.

Table 2. Pearson's correlation coefficient results

Domain-item	Correlation coefficient-domain	Correlation coefficient-scale	Domain-item	Correlation coefficient-domain	Correlation coefficient-scale
Student-centered pedagogy practices	1	.752**	Student-centered assessment practices	1	.936**
1	.566**	.466*	1	.612**	.671**
2	.524*	.453*	2	.715**	.726**
3	.709**	.723**	3	.756**	.737**
4	.735**	.803**	4	.522*	.521*
5	.530*	.587**	5	.735**	.803**
6	.656**	.663**	6	.530*	.587**
7	.522*	.521*	7	.608**	.589**
8	.874**	.567**	8	.784**	.677**
9	.524*	.453*	9	.874**	.567**
10	.585**	.635**	10	.658**	.631**

**Correlation is significant at the .01 level (2-tailed); *Correlation is significant at the .05 level (2-tailed)

Table 2 shows that Pearson's correlation coefficients of items with the total score for the domain ranged between (.522*-.874**). Also, the correlation coefficients of the items with the total score ranged between (.453*-.803**). In addition, the domains with a total score ranged between (.752**-.936**). These results indicate that the questionnaire items, domains, and the whole scale are valid. The correlation values were significant at the (.01 or .05) levels.

3.6. Reliability

The reliability coefficient was calculated on the total score of the questionnaire two methods: Cronbach's alpha equation and test-retest. Test-retest reliability is an indicator of dependability that is acquired by giving the same test to a set of individuals twice over time. The test's reliability over time can then be assessed by correlating the results from times 1 and 2. A group of students might receive the same test twice in order to compute their progress in a particular subject; the second administration might occur a

week following the first. The obtained correlation coefficient would suggest that the scores are consistent [28]. Cronbach's alpha is a way of assessing reliability by comparing the amount of shared variance, or covariance, among the items making up an instrument to the amount of overall variance. The idea is that if the instrument is reliable, there should be a great deal of covariance among the items relative to the variance.

Internal consistency is measured by Cronbach's alpha, a formula created by Lee Cronbach in 1951. Testing the reliability of multiple-question surveys using the Likert scale is known as Cronbach's alpha. These inquiries gauge latent variables, which are concealed or unobservable traits such as conscientiousness, neurosis, or openness. How closely connected a group of test items are to one another can be determined by Cronbach's alpha [29]. The questionnaire was piloted to a sample of 20 teachers who were later excluded from the main study two times with a three-week time span. Then, the reliability coefficients were computed. Table 3 shows the reliability coefficients. The results in Table 3 show that Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient was .93, whereas the test-retest score was .90. These values are high coefficients and indicate that the study tool is reliable.

Table 3. Reliability coefficients for the domains and total score of the study tool

Domain	No. of items	Test-re-test	Cronbach's alpha coefficient
Teachers' attitudes towards student-centered pedagogy practices	10	.90	.87
Teachers' attitudes towards student-centered assessment practices	10	.89	.86
Total score	20	.90	.93

3.7. Statistical processing

The statistical software (SPSS) version (23) was adopted to analyze the study results and answer its questions. The following equations and tests were used: i) Pearson correlation coefficient to check internal consistency; ii) Cronbach alpha and re-test to verify the reliability of the study tool; iii) means, standard deviations, and ranks for answering the research questions; iv) multi-variance analysis (MANOVA) to show differences between the participants' responses due to their gender, experience, degree, and specialization; v) The following grading was adopted for the items and domains of the study tool to determine the degree of agreement based on the range equation: 1-1.80= a very low degree, >1.80-2.60= a low degree, >2.60-3.40= a medium degree, >3.40-4.20= a large degree, >4.20-5= a very large degree; and vi) Finally, the researchers analyzed the qualitative data from the semi-structured interview by the thematic analysis method [30]; the data was checked, read, and classified into main topics. Then, major themes emerged from the topic.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Teachers' attitudes toward student-centred pedagogy practices in the EFL classroom instruction

Table 4 shows the analysis results for the participants' responses to attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy practices in the EFL classroom by means, standard deviations, ranks, and degrees. In Table 4, the results show that the study sample had a very large degree of EFL teachers' attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy practices in the EFL classroom ($M=4.32$, $SD=.555$). This result means that the study sample had very high attitudes toward pedagogy practices focused on students. At the level of items, all values ranged between (3.10-4.64). All items received very large degrees except for the second and last items; they were rated large.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics for student-centered pedagogy practices (teachers' attitudes)

No.	Rank	Item	Means	Standard deviations	Degree
1	1	Interactive classroom activities help implement student-centered pedagogy practices.	4.64	.562	Very large
2	9	Extensive lecturing supports student-centered pedagogy practices.	4.14	1.194	Large
3	2	Collaborative and cooperative learning tasks assist in implementing student-centered pedagogy practices.	4.62	.700	Very large
4	6	Differentiated instructions facilitate student-centered pedagogy practices.	4.29	.979	Very large
5	7	Technology (e-learning apps) to continue discussion outside classroom helps implement student-centered pedagogy practices.	4.25	.969	Very large
6	3	Student-centered pedagogy practices motivate students' self-learning.	4.34	.898	Very large
7	4	Motivational tasks enhance student-centered pedagogy practices.	4.33	.920	Very large
8	10	Role-play activities are good for student-centered pedagogy practices.	4.10	1.215	Large
9	5	Student-centered pedagogy practices encourage student reflection tasks.	4.30	.617	Very large
10	8	Community-based activities ease student-centered pedagogy practices	4.21	.816	Very large
		Total degree	4.32	.617	Very large

Teachers' attitudes towards student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices ... (Mohd Nazim)

4.2. Teachers' attitudes towards student-centred assessment practices

Table 5 shows the analysis results for the participants' responses to EFL teachers' attitudes toward student-centered assessment practices in the EFL classroom by means, standard deviations, ranks, and degrees. In Table 5, the results show that the study sample had a very large degree of EFL teachers' attitudes toward student-centered assessment practices in the EFL classroom ($M=4.29$, $SD=.539$). This result means that the study sample is highly aware of the assessment practices focused on students. At the level of items, all values ranged between (4.05-4.45). The degrees of items ranged between large and very large.

Table 5. Descriptive statistics for student-centered assessment practices (teachers' attitudes)

No.	Rank	Item	Means	Standard deviations	Degree
1	2	Cues, questions, and group discussion help implement student-centered assessment practices	4.42	.705	Very large
2	9	Summarizing, synthesizing, and note taking supports student-centered assessment practices.	4.14	.976	Very large
3	7	Multiple drafts of written assignments assist in implementing student-centered assessment practices.	4.19	.938	Large
4	1	Frequent feedback to students on their progress facilitate student-centered assessment practices.	4.45	.578	Very large
5	4	Multiple varieties of class tests/quizzes help implement student-centered assessment practices.	4.38	.757	Very large
6	6	Shared and independent writing activities are useful student-centered assessment practices.	4.33	.688	Very large
7	5	Student presentations/participations enhance student-centered assessment practices.	4.37	.808	Very large
8	10	Portfolios are encouraged to support student-centered assessment practices	4.05	.832	Large
9	8	Journals are great for student-centered assessment practices.	4.18	.887	Large
10	3	Self-assessment ease student-centered assessment practices	4.41	.761	Very large
		Total degree	4.29	.539	Very large

4.3. Teachers' responses to student-centred pedagogy and assessment practices by their demographic variables

Table 6 presents the results of the MANOVA test for the differences in the study sample's responses to student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in the EFL classroom by the variables of gender, experience, degree, and specialization. Based on the results in Table 6, there were no significant differences at (.05) between the study sample's responses to teachers' attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in the EFL classroom attributed to their gender, specialization, degree, and experience. This result indicates that the respondents' demographic variables did not influence their responses to teachers' attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices.

Table 6. MANOVA analysis results for EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices by variables

Source	Dependent variable	Type I sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Gender	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered pedagogy practices	.413	1	.413	1.142	.289
	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered assessment practices	.286	1	.286	.983	.325
	Total	.008	1	.008	.023	.879
Specialization	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered pedagogy practices	1.036	2	.518	1.433	.246
	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered assessment practices	.891	2	.446	1.533	.224
	Total	.588	2	.294	.830	.441
Degree	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered pedagogy practices	2.038	2	1.019	2.818	.067
	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered assessment practices	.516	2	.258	.888	.416
	Total	1.767	2	.883	2.494	.090
Experience	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered pedagogy practices	.018	1	.018	.048	.826
	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered assessment practices	.041	1	.041	.139	.710
	Total	.955	1	.955	2.695	.105
Error	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered pedagogy practices	23.868	66	.362		
	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered assessment practices	19.192	66	.291		
	Total	23.379	66	.354		
Total	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered pedagogy practices	1389.210	73			
	EFL teachers' attitudes for student-centered assessment practices	1366.400	73			
	Total	1196.698	73			

4.4. Teachers' views of student-centred pedagogy and assessment practices in enhancing English as a foreign language classroom instruction efficacy

Teachers' views of the role of student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in enhancing EFL classroom instruction efficacy were qualitatively analyzed. The findings of the content analysis of the semi-structured interview showed that the interviewees presented some ways in which student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices would enhance EFL classroom instruction efficacy. Accordingly, the interviewees expressed that the EFL classroom instruction efficacy can improve in that students are more active, cooperative, responsible, engaged, communicative, and free. To detail, students will be responsible for their learning and making decisions. They will choose what and how to learn. They will interact more with their peers and teachers. They will be able to self-study learning materials. They are more encouraged to think for themselves as shown in the following excerpts:

- T1: *“When practices of the pedagogies and assessments revolve around the students, students will more active and cooperative as these practices push them to take responsibly for their education and also they feel that they are major contributors to the process of learning the English language.”*
- T2: *“I see, they provide students with the choice of what they learn and how they learn it. Create individualized learning at times. Allow students to take charge of their own learning and make decisions.”*
- T3: *“Students get enough opportunity to interact with peers as well as teachers.”*
- T5: *“Well, keep students attached help teachers evaluate learning progress through students' improvement enhance self-study.”*
- T6: *“Student-centered learning gives students the opportunity to decide two things: what material they learn and how they learn it.”*
- T7: *“Okay, students who participate in student-centered learning have the choice of what they learn and how they learn it. Because students perform better when they are encouraged to think rather than having their thinking done for them.”*
- T9: *“It helps to deliver the material to the students in an effective way.”*
- T12: *“It works to encourage students to learn EFL, especially by dividing them into groups or acting.”*
- T14: *“Motivate creativity and variety of self-study processes.”*

5. DISCUSSION

The results showed that the study sample (EFL teachers) had very positive attitudes towards pedagogy and assessment practices focused on students. Reasons for the current results can be attributed to the fact that the teachers who took part in the study were competent, with the majority holding advanced degrees in applied linguistics or English language teaching (ELT) with rich years of experience instructing EFL students. They understand that a student-centered approach to teaching prioritizes the wants and needs of the students. Moreover, the findings of this study are in line with the research [16], who demonstrated positive attitudes of the EFL teachers toward student-centered learning. In addition, the results of this study are consistent with previous study [23], whose findings indicated that both students and teachers had positive attitudes toward implementing learner centered pedagogy. Likewise, the findings of this study align with the research [16], who noted that there were positive attitudes of English language teachers towards student-centered learning. The results of this study are also consistent with the study [31], who claim that although teachers and students hold positive attitudes toward student-centered approach, they still encounter several issues that prevent the application of the student-centered approach in the classroom. In the same way, the findings of the current study are concordant with the result findings [32], which showed that many teachers used a teacher-centered method in both teaching and assessment practices.

However, the results of this paper disagree with the research [33], who confirmed that teachers hardly implemented student centered pedagogy. Moreover, the findings of this study's analysis are in contrast with another research [34], which noted that reservations have been expressed that assessment procedures are not evolving at the same rate as other aspects of educational initiatives. Besides, the results of this research contradict the findings [35], who concluded that student centered approach was not exercised in the Iranian context. Likewise, the results disagree with a study [36], which showed that a student-centered approach was not employed while assessing students in the study context.

In addition, the demographic variables, including gender, experience, degree, and specialization had no significant role in affecting the teachers' attitudes towards student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices. Reasons for the current results, perhaps, are based on the fact that the participants in this study have qualifications in ELT, and that might be a factor for no significant difference in the current study

findings. Another reason may be attributed to the participants' experience which motivated them to have a very positive attitude toward the student-centered approach. This is also worth noting that the researchers were unable to find any research that might either support or contradict the findings of this study except for gender and experience. Hence, the findings of this study support [23], whose findings indicated that there was no significant difference between the teachers' attitudes and mean scores based on their years of experience. Likewise, the results of this study are similar to previous research [11], who found that gender does not influence the attitude of teachers. However, the findings of this study contrast with Westberg [37] findings which indicate that females favored a teacher-centered approach, while males chose student-centered class environments. Finally, teachers' views of the role of student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in enhancing EFL classroom instruction efficacy showed that the interviewees presented some ways in which student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices would enhance EFL classroom instruction efficacy. The interviewees expressed that the EFL classroom instruction efficacy can improve where students are more active, cooperative, responsible, engaged, communicative, and free. To detail, students will be responsible for their learning and making decisions. They will choose what and how to learn. They will interact more with their peers and teachers. They will be able to self-study learning materials.

6. CONCLUSION

The study surveyed teachers' attitudes towards pedagogy and assessment practices in the EFL classroom from the EFL teachers' viewpoint. The results showed that the study sample (EFL teachers) perceive very high attitudes towards pedagogy and assessment practices focused on students. In addition, the interviewees expressed that the EFL classroom instruction efficacy can improve in that students are more active, cooperative, responsible, engaged, communicative, and free. It was, further, noted that student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices make students more responsible for their learning and making decisions, choose what and how to learn, interact more with their peers and teachers, and be able to self-study learning materials. Thus, it can be assumed that teachers who have a favorable attitude toward active learning can positively influence their students' attitudes. This can be accomplished by the teachers' helpful behavior, resourcefulness, enthusiasm. However, it would be preferable to increase the professionalism of the teachers in favor of student-centered strategies.

The results show that the study sample had a very large degree for EFL teachers' attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy practices in the EFL classroom. All items received very large degrees except for the second and last items; they were rated large. Also, the results reveal that the study sample had a very large degree of attitude toward student-centered assessment practices in the EFL classroom. At the level of items, they ranged between large and very large. There was no significant difference between the study sample's responses to teachers' attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices in the EFL classroom attributed to their gender, specialization, academic degree, and experience. This result indicates that the respondents' demographic variables did not influence their responses to student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices. Additionally, the results of the content analysis of the semi-structured interview revealed that the interviewees presented ways in which student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices would enhance EFL classroom instruction efficacy. Accordingly, the interviewees expressed that the EFL classroom instruction efficacy can improve the condition in that students are more active, cooperative, responsible, engaged, communicative, and free. To detail, students will be responsible for their learning and making decisions. They will choose what and how to learn. They will interact more with their peers and teachers. They will be able to self-study learning materials. They will be more encouraged to think for themselves. Hence, the researchers are also of the opinion that teachers' positive attitudes assist in employing student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices. As presented in this study that teachers' attitudes are a major factor in determining how student-centered pedagogy and assessment practices would be activated in the classroom.

Due to recent developments and shifts in classroom instructions, one of the key implications for teachers is that the traditional educational methodologies can no longer fulfill the ever-changing needs of EFL learners. Therefore, to stay up-to-date on the most recent changes to the paradigm shift from teacher-centeredness to student-centeredness, EFL teachers must have positive attitudes toward student-centered pedagogy and assessment procedures. Results cannot be assumed to be generalizable due to the participant restrictions since all study participants were instructors. If students and other stakeholders are involved, the outcomes of a study like this may alter. The researchers suggest teachers' attitudes in employing learner-centered pedagogy and assessment practices as a blended mode should be a subject of future studies. Also, further studies are recommended considering different variables since the teachers' attitudes toward employing learner-centered pedagogy and assessment practices are crucial.

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